

TABLE 1—PHENYL FURYLACRYLATES

R	m.p. (°C)	Mol. Formula	Analysis(%)			
			Calc.		Found	
			C	H	C	H
H	42-3	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ O ₃	72.90	4.67	72.89	4.58
CH ₃	52	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃	73.69	5.26	73.62	5.19
NO ₂	158	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₃ N	60.23	3.47	60.14	3.88

Naphthyl furylacrylates : 1- and 2-Naphthyl furylacrylates were obtained by condensing 1- and 2-naphthols with furylacrylic acid by the method given above.

1-Naphthyl furylacrylate, m.p. 45°; yield 92%. (Found : C, 77.21; H, 4.44; C₁₇H₁₂O₃ requires C, 77.27; H, 4.55%), 2-Naphthyl furylacrylate, m.p. 70°; yield 95%. (Found : C, 77.18; H, 4.49; C₁₇H₁₂O₃ requires C, 77.27; H, 4.55%).

Coumarin (2-Oxo-2H-1-benzopyran) and 6-substituted derivatives (Table 2) :

The respective furylacrylates prepared as above (3 g) were dissolved in dry chlorobenzene (30 ml) and mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (9 g). The mixture was heated under reflux on a water-bath for 1.5 to 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was decomposed by the addition of ice and dil. HCl and extracted with CHCl₃. The chloroform extract was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated to yield the product which was purified by crystallisation in ethanol or chromatographed over a silica gel column, employing hexane, benzene, chloroform and methanol, in the order, as eluants in varying proportions.

Benzocoumarins (2-oxo-2H-1-naphthopyrans) :

1- and 2-Naphthyl furylacrylates when subjected to the above method gave respectively 7, 8-benzocoumarin, m.p. 140-1°; yield 52% (Found : C, 79.46; H, 3.92, C₁₃H₈O₂ requires C, 79.57; H, 3.99%), IR (ν_{max}^{KBr} in cm⁻¹) : 1724; UV (in 95% EtOH), λ_{max} 219 nm, and λ_{min} 308 nm.

5,6-Benzocoumarin, m.p. 118°; yield 46% (C₁₃H₈O₂; Found : C, 79.51; H, 3.95%), IR (KBr) : 1720 cm⁻¹ UV (in 95% EtOH) λ_{max} 231 nm, and λ_{min} 317 nm.

[IR (KBr) : 1700, 1720 and 1735 cm⁻¹ for R=H, -CH₃ and -NO₂ respectively (>C=O) ;

UV_{max}^{MeOH} ; 312 nm (R=H), 310 nm (R=CH₃), and 314 nm (R=NO₂)]

TABLE 2—6-SUBSTITUTED COUMARINS

R	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Mol. Formula	Analysis(%)			
				Calc.		Found	
				C	H	C	H
H	70	73	C ₉ H ₆ O ₂	73.96	4.11	73.89	4.02
CH ₃	74-5	65	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂	75.01	5.0	74.87	4.92
NO ₂	185-6	78	C ₉ H ₅ O ₄ N	56.54	2.62	56.42	2.52

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References

1. T. MANIMARAN, T. K. THIRUVENGADI and V. T. RAMAKRISHNAN, *Synthesis*, 1975, 789.
2. T. MANIMARAN and V. T. RAMAKRISHNAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **18B**, 78, 924.
3. C. M. CHRISTIAN and G. O. AMIN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 715.
4. J. D. SIMPSON and S. S. ISRAELSTAM, *Chem. Abs.*, 1951, **45**, 6196d; J. D. SIMPSON and H. STEPHEN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1382.

Malhotra and Katoch's "Solvates" of Alkali Acetates with Acetic Anhydride— A Reinvestigation

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WE were fascinated by the report of Malhotra and Katoch¹ on the successful synthesis of MOAc-Ac₂O complexes where M is an alkali cation and Ac₂O denotes acetic anhydride. To clear our own doubts we repeated the work and found that the MOAc products (M=Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺ and NH₄⁺) were in fact M(OAc, HOAc) acid salts; the products obtained by these workers¹ by the reaction of MOAc with Ac₂O were the same as we obtained

TABLE—MELTING POINTS AND ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF SOME MOAc-Ac₂O PRODUCTS WHICH ARE INFAC^t M(OAc,HOAc) ACID SALTS

Compound	Melting point, °C			C and H percentage of solvates ¹				C and H percentage calc. by us			
	as in	as in	found	C		H		for MOAc-Ac ₂ O		for M(OAc,HOAc)	
	ref. 1	lit ²	by us	Calc.	(found)	Calc.	(found)	C	H	C	H
Li(OAc,HOAc)	105-7	—	106	36.08	(35.84)	4.49	(4.36)	42.86	5.36	38.09	5.56
Na(OAc,HOAc)	06	—	96	39.33	(39.16)	4.16	(4.02)	39.13	4.89	33.80	4.93
K(OAc,HOAc)	144	144	144	41.08	(40.92)	3.87	(3.64)	36.00	4.50	30.38	4.43
NH ₄ (OAc,HOAc)	66	66	65	34.12	(33.82)	6.16	(6.04)	40.22	7.26	35.04	8.03

by the reaction of MOAc with AcOH (1 : 1) in ethanol². Infrared spectra of the K⁺-products obtained from both the type of reaction mixtures, for example, are the same (see figure). Each spectrum is ill defined in the finger print region which is indicative of the product being an acid salt^{3,4}. An elaborated discussion provided by Malhotra and Katoch on IR spectra, which has been made in an attempt to authenticate the products to be MOAc-Ac₂O complexes, is therefore an irrelevant exercise.

Melting points reported by these authors are the same which we found and the literature⁵ reported (Table) for the acid acetates, M(OAc, HOAc), of the concerned cations; 06° instead of 96° for the Na-products is understandably a lapse of proof reading.

For all the four products in question, the "calculated" percentage of elements (see Table)

Fig. Infrared spectra of the KOAc-products obtained from (a) KOAc-Ac₂O according to ref. 1, and (b) KOAc-HOAc (1 : 1) in ethanol.

reported by these authors is incorrect even with respect to MOAc-Ac₂O complexes as seen from the comparison of values we report in the Table. It is interestingly significant that their 'found' values

have constantly tied up with these incorrect values and in no case with the correct values for M(OAc, HOAc) or MOAc-Ac₂O species.

The MOAc salts of Li⁺ and Na⁺ exist hydrated whereas those of K⁺ and NH₄⁺ are hygroscopic. The authors do not mention about the precautions they undertook to avoid the involvement of this water during 24 hours of the reaction between MOAc and Ac₂O they carried out¹. This suggests that during "complexation", Ac₂O gets hydrolysed to produce AcOH and the latter interacts with M⁺OAc⁻ to produce M(OAc, HOAc) as we illustrated in EtOH media.

We were interested only in the study of the concerned four cations for all of which M(OAc, HOAc) salt instead of MOAc-Ac₂O complexes have been found to form. Rb⁺ and Cs⁺ should be rather more prone to the formation of M(OAc, HOAc) salts because in the presence of these low charge density cations the AcO...HOAc conjugation is expected to be more pronounced⁶. Therefore, there is no surprise if similar wrong interpretations of the results have been made in the case of other complexes reported in the quoted paper¹.

References

1. K. C. MALHOTRA and D. S. KATOCH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1182.
2. N. S. POONIA and M. R. TRUTER, *J. Chem. Soc. (Dalton)*, 1972, 1791.
3. D. HADZI, A. NOVAK and J. E. GORDIN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 1118.
4. D. HADZI, *Pure appl. Chem.*, 1965, **11**, 435.
5. R. C. WEAST (Editor-in-chief), "Handbook of Chemistry and Physics", 46th Edition, The Chemical Rubber Co., Ohio, 1965-66, pp. B-149, B-205.
6. N. S. POONIA, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1977, **36**, 268; N. S. POONIA and A. V. BAJAJ, *Chem. Rev.*, 1979, **79**, 389. issue.

**Chemical Constituents of the Roots of
Millingtonia hortensis Linn. and
Acacia nilotica (Linn.) Del.**

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MILLINGTONIA *hortensis* Linn. (Bignoniaceae) commonly known as 'Akash Neem' or 'Neem Chameli' is a well known plant. The perusal of literature revealed that the stem of this plant has been investigated by Joshi *et al.*¹. The present work deals with the isolation and characterization of various chemical constituents from the root.

Acacia nilotica (Linn.) Del. (Leguminosae) is an important medicinal plant² and used as an anthelmintic, and in bronchitis, diarrhoea, etc.^{3,4}. Some work has been reported on stem⁵, so we undertook a systematic chemical investigation of the bark and heartwood of root.

Experimental

Chemical Constituents from Millingtonia hortensis Linn. :

Air-dried coarsely powdered root (4.5 kg) was extracted thrice with hot petroleum-ether (60-80°). The concentrated extract was chromatographed over silica-gel. Elution with solvents of increasing polarity gave the following compounds.

Hentriacontane :

The petroleum ether eluate afforded hentriacontane, crystallized from ethyl acetate as colourless crystals, m.p. 68°; negative TNM test; M^+ 436; IR $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1460 and a doublet at 730-720 cm^{-1} ; identical (mmp, TLC) with an authentic sample.

Lapachol :

Elution of the column with pet. ether-benzene (3:1) afforded lapachol, m.p. 138-39° (benzene); violet red colour with ferric chloride and deep red solution was obtained with aqueous sodium hydroxide; UV $\lambda_{\max}$ (EtOH) 251, 276, 329 nm; IR $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3335, 1660, 1637, 1591 cm^{-1} ; identical (mmp, TLC & IR) with an authentic sample.

Hentriacontanol-1 :

Further elution of the column with pet. ether-benzene (1:1) yielded white crystalline, m.p. 84° (MeOH); negative TNM test; M^+ 452; IR $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3280, 1470 and a doublet at 730-720 cm^{-1} etc.; Acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Pyr.}$), m.p. 69-70°; identical (mmp, TLC) with an authentic sample.

β -sitosterol :

Elution of the column with pet. ether-benzene (1:3) gave β -sitosterol, shining needles, m.p. 136-37° ($\text{CHCl}_3/\text{MeOH}$) gave positive Liebermann-Burchard test for sterol; IR $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3400, 1050, 800, 715 cm^{-1} , etc.; Acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Pyr.}$), m.p. 125-26°; Benzoate ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCl}/\text{Pyr.}$), m.p. 143-4°; identical (mmp, TLC & IR) with an authentic sample.

Paulownin :

Further elution of the column with benzene-ethyl-acetate (3:1) gave paulownin, m.p. 104° (benzene); Positive Labat and Hansen tests; Negative to TNM and FeCl_3 tests; IR $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3400, 1610, 1265, 970, 780 cm^{-1} , etc.; Acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Pyr.}$), m.p. 143°; identical (mmp, TLC & IR) with an authentic sample.

Chemical Constituents from Acacia nilotica (Linn.) Del. Root Bark : Completely dried and coarsely powdered root-bark was exhaustively extracted with benzene. The concentrated benzene extract fractionated into soluble and insoluble petroleum ether fractions. The soluble portion was chromatographed over silica-gel, elution being made with solvents of increasing polarity and the following compounds were obtained :

Octacosanol : Elution of the column with pet. ether-benzene (3:1) furnished octacosanol, white crystalline compound, m.p. 83° (Pet. ether); No colour with TNM; IR $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3360, 2960, 2820, 1460, 1050, 730 and 720 cm^{-1} ; Acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Pyr.}$), m.p. 64°; identical (mmp, TLC & IR) with an authentic sample.

β -amyrin : Further elution of the column with pet. ether-benzene (1:1) yielded β -amyrin, m.p. 196-97° (EtOH); yellow colour with TNM; Positive Liebermann-Burchard and Noller's test; IR $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3360, 2960, 2880, 1650, 1465, 1040, 890 cm^{-1} ; Acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Pyr.}$), m.p. 238°; Benzoate ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCl}/\text{Pyr.}$) m.p. 228°; identical (mmp, TLC & IR) with an authentic sample.

β -sitosterol : Further elution of the column with pet. ether-benzene (1:3) furnished β -sitosterol, m.p. 136° ($\text{CHCl}_3/\text{MeOH}$); Acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Pyr.}$), m.p. 125-26° identical (mmp, TLC & IR) with an authentic sample.

Betulin : Elution of the column with benzene-ethylacetate (3:1) yielded betulin, white shining needles, m.p. 248-49° (EtOH); M^+ 442; Positive Liebermann-Burchard test and Noller's test; Yellow colour with TNM; IR $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3390, 2960, 1650, 1460, 1370 cm^{-1} etc.; Acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Pyr.}$), m.p. 215-16°; identical (mmp, TLC & IR) with an authentic sample.